

A CLASSICAL REVIEW OF YAVAKSHARA IN GHRITA FORMULATIONS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHAKRADATTA

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ABSTRACT

Kshara preparations play an important role in *Ayurveda* for their *Lekhana*, *Bhedana* and *Shodhana* properties and are recognised as effective therapeutic agents. *Yavakshara* (from Yava or Barley) is one of the most frequently used *kshara* and is particularly helpful in the management of diseases associated with a predominance of *kapha dosha* and obstruction. *Ghrita* is considered the best *sneha* due to its *yogavahitva* and *samskara anuvartana* qualities which make it an optimal carrier for the potent *kshara* preparations. *Chakradatta*, a classical ayurvedic text, describes several *Ghrita* formulations containing yavakshara, indicating their therapeutic significance. All of the *Ghrita* formulations with yavakshara were identified and compiled. Their indications and rationale were examined and analysed according of *Ayurvedic* principles. All of these formulations have multiple indications related to *kapha*, *meda*,

or *srotorodha* in regarding to treat conditions such as *Gulma*, *Udara*, *Arsha* and *Mutraghata*. Combining *Ghrita* and *yavakshara* offers the benefits of *Lekhana* and *Bhedana* of *kshara* with the protective and bio-enhancing properties of *Ghrita*, creating a balanced therapeutic approach. Classical analysis indicates that *Ghrita* reduces the *tikshna* nature of *yavakshara*

while concurrently enhancing the effectiveness of *yavakshara*, and therefore both can be used safely for internal consumption. Additional clinical or experimental studies are needed to validate the use of these classical formulations.

KEYWORDS: *Yavakshara, Ghrita, Chakradatta, Gulma, Bhedana.*

INTRODUCTION

Traditional *Ayurveda* provides a comprehensive, evidence-based approach to disease management through many forms of medicines including *kalka, churna, kwatha, sneha* and *kshara*. *Kshara kalpana* is considered one of the most important forms of medication in *Ayurveda* due to its advanced properties of *lekhana, bhedana, deepana* and *pachana*. These properties make it especially useful in managing *kapha*-dominant conditions and diseases involving obstruction. One of the most widely used plant-derived *ksharas* is *yavakshara*, which is prepared from *yava* and has important pharmacological properties including *katu rasa, tikshna* and *laghu guna, ushna virya*, and *kapha-vatashamaka* properties. Because of these properties, *yavakshara* is used successfully in the treatment of a wide variety of conditions, such as *arsha, gulma, udara, mutraghata* and *ashmari*, where both *srotorodha* and increased *medo-kapha* formation are causative factors for the condition.^[1]

Ghrita, because of its *tridoshaghna, yogavahitva*, and *samskara anuvartana* properties is regarded as the best type of *sneha* in *Ayurveda*. It has a unique ability to absorb the pharmacological characteristics of the raw drugs that are processed with it while also significantly increasing their therapeutic effects and safety.^[2] *Ghrita* serves to mitigate the excessive *tikshna* and *ushna* properties of the *kshara*, thus making it much safer when used internally.

The well-known *Ayurvedic* text *Chakradatta* is an important resource for evidence-based therapeutic formulations presented in a concise manner. The text describes several *Ghrita* formulations having *yavakshara* reflecting a thoughtful pharmaceutical approach towards combining potent *kshara* drugs with *sneha* to improve their therapeutic effectiveness. The formulations described in these sections are scattered throughout *Chakradatta* and were not compiled or reviewed in one place.

The purpose of this study is therefore to provide a classical review of the *yavakshara* in *Ghrita* formulations as they are reported in *Chakradatta* including analysis of their

composition, clinical use and potential mechanisms of action according to *Ayurvedic* principles. Such a review is expected to provide a comprehensive understanding of these formulations and serve as a reference for clinicians and researchers while also laying a foundation for future experimental and clinical studies.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Aim: To review *Yavakshara* in *Ghrita* formulations described in *Chakradatta*.

Objectives

1. To compile *Ghrita* formulations having *Yavakshara* from *Chakradatta*.
2. To understand their probable mode of action based on *Ayurvedic* principles.

METHODOLOGY

Ghrita formulations having *Yavakshara* were identified, compiled and analyzed with respect to their ingredients, indications and therapeutic rationale based on *Ayurvedic* principles. This study was conducted as a descriptive, classical literature review focusing on *yavakshara*-containing *Ghrita* formulations described in *Chakradatta*.

Yavakshara in *Ghrita* formulations^[3]

Sr. no.	<i>Ghrita</i>	<i>Rogadhikara</i>	<i>Rogagnata</i>
1.	<i>Dashamoolashatpala Ghrita</i>	<i>Jirna jwara chikitsa</i>	<i>Jwara, Kasa, vata-kapha, pleeharoga, panduroga</i>
2.	<i>Marichyadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani chikitsa</i>	<i>Kasa, shwasa, kshaya, arsha, bhagandara, grahani, pleeha, kapha-vata roga, krumiroga</i>
3.	<i>Mahashatpalaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Grahani chikitsa</i>	<i>Krumi-pleeha-udara-grahani roga, ajirna, kushta, prvahika, kapha-vata roga, panduroga, kshaya, kasa</i>
4.	<i>Chavyadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsharoga chikitsa</i>	<i>Pravahika, gudabhransha, mutrakruchha, vakshanshul</i>
5.	<i>Utpalashatakam Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsharoga chikitsa</i>	<i>Jwara, arsha, pleeha, kasa</i>
6.	<i>Agnighruta</i>	<i>Agnimandya chikitsa</i>	<i>Arsha, gulma, udara, granthi, arbuda, apache, kasa, kapha-meda-vata roga, grahani, bhagandara, shotha</i>
7.	<i>Mastushatpala Ghrita</i>	<i>Agnimandya chikitsa</i>	<i>Mandagni, kapha, gulma</i>
8.	<i>Bruhatagni Ghrita</i>	<i>Agnimandya chikitsa</i>	<i>Arsha, kapha-vataj gulma, slipada, jalodara, shotha, panduroga, kasa, grahani, shwasa</i>
9.	<i>Bruhat kantakari Ghrita</i>	<i>Kasachikitsa</i>	<i>Kapharoga, kasa, shwasa, hikka</i>

		<i>chikitsa</i>	
10.	<i>Dadhikam Ghrita</i>	<i>Shooladhikara chikitsa</i>	<i>Gulma, arsha, pleeha, hridroga, parshwashoola, yonishoola</i>
11.	<i>Dhatrishatpalakam Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulmadhikara chikitsa</i>	<i>Gulma</i>
12.	<i>Bharangishatpala Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma chikitsa</i>	<i>Gulma, udara, Aruchi, bhagandara, kapha-vata roga</i>
13.	<i>Ksheershatpala Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma chikitsa</i>	<i>Kaphaja gulma, grahani, panduroga, pleeha, kasa, jwara</i>
14.	<i>Bhallataka Ghrita</i>	<i>Gulma chikitsa</i>	<i>Kaphaj gulma, pleeha, panduroga, shwasa, kasa, grahani</i>
15.	<i>Kulatthadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Arsha chikitsa</i>	<i>Ashmari, Mutrakriccha, Mutraghata</i>
16.	<i>Dashamoolashatpalakam Ghrita</i>	<i>Udara chikitsa</i>	<i>Udara, Gulma</i>
17.	<i>Chitrak Ghrita</i>	<i>Pleehyakrutaroga chikitsa</i>	<i>Pleeha, Gulma, Udara, Adhmana, Panduroga, Aruchi, Jwara, Basti-hruday-parshwashoola, Udavarta, Peenas, Arsha, Shotha, Agnideepana</i>
18.	<i>Maharohitaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Pleehyakrutaroga chikitsa</i>	<i>Yakrita, Pleeha, Udara, Aruchi, Panduroga, Kamala, Atisara</i>
19.	<i>Punarnavadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Shotha chikitsa</i>	<i>Shotha</i>
20.	<i>Chitrakadya Ghrita</i>	<i>Shotha chikitsa</i>	<i>Arsha, Gulma, Shoth, Mutrakriccha, Agnideepan</i>
21.	<i>Saureshwar Ghrita</i>	<i>Shlipada chikitsa</i>	<i>Apachi, Gandamala, antravruddhi, Arbuda, Grahanidosha, Shotha, Arsha, Agnideepana, Krumi</i>
22.	<i>Changeri Ghrita</i>	<i>Kshudrarog chikitsa</i>	<i>Gudabhransha</i>

DISCUSSION

Kshara kalpana represents a unique form of *Ayurveda* therapeutics as a result of its excellent effects of *lekhana*, *bhedana* and *shodhana*. *Yavakshara*, prepared from *Yava* (Barley), is especially beneficial in conditions such as *kapha* predominance, vitiation of medo-dhatu, or obstruction of bodily channels. The incorporation of *Yavakshara* into *Ghrita*-based formulations described in *Chakradatta* represents a well-planned pharmaceutical strategy intended to optimize therapeutic action while minimizing the adverse effects associated with the internal use of *kshara*.

From the literature review, it can be determined that *Ghrita* formulations having *Yavakshara* are generally indicated in conditions such as *gulma*, *udara*, *arsha*, *mutraghata* and *ashmari*.

These pathological entities have in common *srotovarodha*, impaired *agni*, and an accumulation of *kapha* and *meda*. The *tikshna*, *laghu* and *ushna* properties of *yavakshara* help in breaking down blockages and restoring normal flow of *doshas* and *mala*. Also the *amla varga* helps neutralize the excessive amount of alkaline *kshara* through controlled buffering of the acid and alkali. From a modern viewpoint, the buffering effect of acidic ingredients can neutralize the alkaline *kshara* to decrease the corrosive qualities while maintaining the therapeutic effects. *Ghrita* is an essential part of these formulations, as it provides an effective route of entry into the body and a means to protect it from irritation. In addition, *Ghrita's yogavahitva* allows deeper penetration into tissues where the active components of *Yavakshara* can exert their effects; its *samskara anuvartana* quality helps in assimilating and enhancing the properties of raw drugs. Moreover, *Ghrita* reduces *tikshnata* and *ushnata* from *Yavakshara* thereby minimizing the possibility of harming the gastrointestinal mucosa and making this formulation suitable for internal use.

From an *Ayurvedic* pharmacodynamics point of view, the combination of *Yavakshara* with *Ghrita* produces a synergistic effect. With the actions of *yavakshara* producing *kapha-medahara* and *srotoshodhana*^[4] and *Ghrita* providing nourishment to the tissues while supporting *agni* without aggravating *pitta*^[5], their combined action is particularly useful in treating long-standing or chronic conditions which induce both *shodhana* and *shamana* effects simultaneously.

The inclusion of these formulations in *Chakradatta* highlights their importance in *Ayurvedic* therapeutics from a practical point of view. The concise yet purposeful description of these formulations suggests their frequent use in clinical practice during the period of the text. However, despite their classical significance, there is lack of systematic compilation and scientific analysis in contemporary research.

Thus this present review attempts to bridge this gap in the literature and consists of a compilation and analysis of *Yavakshara* containing *Ghrita* formulations referenced in *Chakradatta*. Understanding their classical rationale not only aids clinicians in rational prescription but also provides a foundation for future pharmacological, experimental and clinical studies to validate their efficacy and safety.

CONCLUSION

Yavakshara in *Ghrita* formulations found in *Chakradatta* demonstrate an effective and evidence-based approach to treatment of various diseases by providing a comprehensive understanding of *Ayurvedic* pharmaceuticals. *Yavakshara* combined with *Ghrita* forms a balanced preparation where the cleansing actions of *kshara* that is *lekhana*, *bhedana* and *shodhana* work alongside the nourishing and protective nature of *Ghrita*, enhancing both effectiveness and safety. These formulations are mainly used in *kapha*-dominant and obstructive conditions like *gulma*, *udara* and *ashmari*, which involve channel blockage (*srotorodha*), *meda* accumulation and impaired *Agni*.

The classical rationale that serves as a basis for these formulations is clinically relevant and applicable to current *Ayurvedic* practice. This systematic review consolidates all *Ghrita* formulations having *Yavakshara* from *Chakradatta* into one primary reference source for clinicians and scholars. There is a need for further pharmacological, experimental and clinical studies to scientifically validate these classical formulations and demonstrate their therapeutic capabilities through evidence-based practice within an *Ayurvedic* context. The concept of various *kshara* preparations along with *Ghrita*, as mentioned in other classical *Ayurvedic granthas* remains insufficiently studied and therefore requires further systematic literary analysis and experimental research to validate its safety, mechanism of action and clinical significance.

In summary, *Yavakshara-Ghrita* formulations from *Chakradatta* offer an effective means of addressing both *kapha*-dominant and obstructive disorders. This classical review highlights their therapeutic importance and provides a foundation for further clinical and experimental studies.

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